

EXTRACTION METHODS OF VALUE-ADDED COMPOUNDS FROM BIOMASSES

Tutku Taşçı Çilak^{1*}, Sylvia Fasse¹, Sanketkumar Raval¹, Mette Hedegaard Thomsen², Axel Gottschalk¹

¹ Department of Process Engineering, University of Applied Sciences Bremerhaven, Germany
An der Karlstadt 8, 27568, Bremerhaven

² Department for Energy Technology, Aalborg University – Esbjerg Campus, Denmark
Niels Bohrs Vej 8, 6700 Esbjerg, Denmark

*Email address corresponding author: ttasci@hs-bremerhaven.de

ABSTRACT: Since there are vast applications possible for bioactive compounds in the pharma, food, and chemical industry; the most efficient, economical, and environmentally viable extraction method needs to be applied to valorize biomass. Many new methods as well as conventional methods have been developed with high recovery of bioactive components from biomasses. However, the chosen method should be evaluated in an economic way with a comparison of other methods to be implementable on industrial scale as well. This review paper aims to determine the state of the art for extraction methods of value-added compounds from biomasses with the focus on critical parameters such as cost, yield, extraction time, and environmental friendliness of the process.

Keywords: biomass, biobased products, value-added compounds, biorefinery, solid-liquid extraction

1 INTRODUCTION

A biorefinery concept is an approach for the production of value-added compounds such as biochemicals, biofuels, heat, and electricity with the utilization of biomass [1]. Biorefineries require green and sustainable techniques to separate the target compounds from the raw material in economic, social, and environmental aspects for large production scales [2]. In biorefineries, biomass conversion processes, separation, and purification of the biomass components are great of importance. This can be the biggest factor which effects success and commercialization of biorefineries [3]. Hence, the overall level of integration in biorefinery increases the economic value of the biorefineries. Economical and environmentally sustainable options for integrated biorefineries can be provided by development in feedstocks, conversion processes (biochemical, chemical, and thermochemical), and their integration with powerful downstream separations. Thereby, high value-added compounds together with high energy biofuels will increase the sustainability and interest of biomass [4].

Biomass is the most suitable and renewable resource for the recovery of value-added compounds and there are many methods to extract or isolate value-added compounds from biomass [5]. Biomass has many natural products such as waxes, fatty acids, polyacetylenes, terpenoids, steroids, essential oils, phenolics, flavonoids, tannins, anthocyanins, quinones, coumarins, lignans, alkaloids, and glycosidic derivatives [6]. Therefore, biomass is a good source for pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and food industries and gains more demand day by day worldwide. There is a big need to improve how biomass can be valorized in a more sustainable and economic way [7]. A sustainable biorefinery concept has durable and economical utilization of biomass resources to produce bio-energy and value-added components which are used in many industrial applications. Various types of biomass from agricultural, forestry, and food industry waste, like agricultural plant stems, wood and wood residue, organic residue, forestry residue, etc. can be used in biorefinery [8].

Extraction is an important process step to recover value-added compounds, which plays a crucial role in pharmaceutical, cosmetic, nutraceutical, or bioenergy industries. Hence, there is a huge demand for new extraction technologies to reduce energy consumption,

meet the legal requirements on emissions, fulfill product safety, and increase the quality of products [9]. Therefore, reduced extraction time, less energy consumption, and less use of organic solvents have become the main tasks in the industries. Conventional extraction methods such as hydro-distillation, Soxhlet extraction, maceration, percolation, infusion, and decoction are used for many years. However, they have some drawbacks such as low efficiency, non-selectivity, time-consuming, high-energy requirement, high solvent usage, and thermal decomposition of thermolabile products. Therefore, to overcome these drawbacks, novel extraction methods such as supercritical CO₂ extraction, microwave-assisted extraction, ultrasound-assisted extraction, enzyme-assisted extraction, pressurized fluid extraction, or a combination of these approaches can be a good alternative in biorefineries [10].

This paper is published within the framework of the EU Horizon 2020 project AQUACOMBINE which is funded by the European Commission under the Grant Agreement number 862834. The Aquacombine Project aims to introduce biorefinery new and promising halophyte feedstock/residue and to demonstrate how halophytes turn into a profitable biorefinery. Halophytes provide benefits in terms of conservation of freshwater, generation of edible food, fodder, oil, and other valuable by-products. Halophyte biomasses have a great potential for value-added compounds such as protein, amino acids, alkaloids, fatty acids and lipids, flavonoids, phenolics, quinines, tannins, terpenoids, steroids, saponins, and coumarins [11, 12]. Therefore, this paper aims to give a comprehensive review of the various existing extraction methods from different types of biomasses to contribute AQUACOMBINE project because choosing an economic and eco-friendly extraction method for value-added compounds will be really important for the project's aims to be implemented at commercial scale. Hence, this paper introduces conventional and unconventional extraction methods for value-added compounds from various biomasses in the literature. More specifically and in detail, this review represents and discusses unconventional methods with details on the working principle of methods, challenges and benefits, applications in industry, and effective parameters of the process. Besides this, a comparative evaluation of the unconventional techniques is also presented.

2 PRINCIPLES OF EXTRACTION PROCESS

The solid-liquid extraction includes three process steps; (1) internal transport process (intraparticle diffusion); the solvent penetrates into the solid matrix, (2) dissolution processes; the solute dissolves in the solvents, (3) external mass transfer process; the solute is diffused out [13, 14]. In the feed material, the extract can be a solid or liquid form which is attached to the carrier material as a fine dispersion like in coffee. The feed material can be porous and have many capillaries. The solvent penetrates into the material through the capillaries and dissolves the extract at the beginning of the extraction. The equalization of the extract solution in the feed material and the extract solution of the surrounding the solid is achieved during solid-liquid extraction [15]. Until the equilibrium concentrations in the solid and liquid phases are achieved, the mass transfer continues from the solid phase to the liquid phase. A particular amount of solvent is kept inside the residue due to adhesive forces after the extraction process is completed. Also, this adherent solvent has a quantity of extract which remains in the extraction residue after the solvent has been removed. Therefore, there is no total extraction process without losses in practice [15].

To increase the efficiency of the extraction process, solubility and diffusivity should be improved in the process. The factors that affect the extraction process are directly related to diffusivity, mass transfer, and solubility phenomena. There are five important factors that affect the extraction process and yield of the target compound to extract; (1) operating temperature; (2) particle size of raw material; (3) extraction time; (4) solvent to solid ratio; (5) solvent properties [14].

The temperature has a big effect on solid-liquid extraction. Higher temperature provides higher solubility of the solid material being extracted and a higher extraction rate by increasing its diffusivity. On the other hand, the higher temperature might cause high solvent losses due to evaporation, extraction of some undesirable compounds due to degradation of thermolabile compounds, and damaging some sensitive components in plant material [14, 16]. Furthermore, a higher temperature than required can cause energy consumption and as a result of this, it can cause higher costs as well. For this reason, the optimal operating temperature should be chosen according to the target compound to extract in order to have a more efficient process.

Size reduction of the solid material is preferred by the solid-liquid extraction process. With size reduction of the solid is aimed to make the solute more accessible to the solvent. The size of solid material can be reduced by grinding, crushing, flaking, or cutting into pieces. Thus, reduced particle size increases surface area per unit volume of the solid to be leached and reduces the distance to be traversed within the solid by the solvent and the extract. For example, using grinding can be obtained very fine size particles but these fine particles might cause the packing of solids, thus the free flow of solvent is prevented during the extraction [14, 16]. Hence, suitable and optimal particle sizes should be chosen to increase the extraction rate.

Solvent plays an important role in solid-liquid extraction. Many factors should be considered for the selection of solvents such as capacity, selectivity, chemical inertness, thermophysical properties, flammability, toxicity, cost, and availability. To increase the quality and yield of the product, the correct combination of solvent

and solute should be achieved. The compatibility of solute and solvent can be determined by having similar functional groups. For example, non-polar solutes normally dissolve better in non-polar solvents [14, 17]. A good solvent should provide a high yield and purity of product without undesired by-products. Additionally, the solvents should have low specific heat and low latent heat of vaporization to ease separation and recovery after the extraction process is completed [16]. Furthermore, the selection of solvent should be fulfilled some regulations, laws, consumer acceptance, and environmental concerns regarding application areas such as pharmacy, cosmetic, or food industry [16].

Sufficient extraction time is required to achieve the desired amount of the target compound. The yield of the target compound is increased with increasing time within a certain range. When the extraction process reaches the equilibrium conditions, increasing time will not have any effect on the yield of the product [14].

Another important factor in solid-liquid extraction is the solid to solvent ratio. The higher the solvent to solid ratio is, the higher the extraction yield is. However, a higher ratio than required will lead to excessive solvent and require a very long time to achieve enough concentration of product [14]. Therefore, the amount of solute in solid material requires a certain amount of solvent to be extracted [17].

3 SOLID-LIQUID EXTRACTION METHODS

An effective extraction method is maximizing the isolation of the target compound with minimal degradation [18]. Many factors have to be considered to choose the best method of separation for target compound from raw material such as physical-chemical properties of raw material and target compounds, desired purity, selectivity, stability, and more sustainable and economically available technology [2]. All these methods have common aims; (1) to extract only target compounds in as high as possible concentration; (2) to increase the selectivity of analytical methods; (3) to have less extraction time; (4) to have solvent recovery in an economic way.

3.1 Conventional techniques

Conventional techniques have been for many years used to extract bioactive components from different raw materials. These techniques are (1) hydro-distillation which is further divided into three categories; (i) water distillation; (ii) water and steam distillation; (iii) direct steam distillation; (2) Soxhlet extraction; (3) maceration; (4) percolation; (5) infusion, (6) decoction; and (7) hot continuous extraction [19]. The maceration method is an easy process of a pulverized sample with the solvent in a closed system by agitation at room temperature for long period. Separation is required by using either filtration, decantation, or clarification after the maceration extraction method. The main drawback of this technique is the high amount of solvents and the long extraction time required [20, 21]. The percolation method is similar to the maceration method but more efficient than it since it is a continuous process where the solvent is continuously added and dropped from the top to bottom, thus the extract is simultaneously collected. In the percolation extraction, filtration is not required because the percolation extractor is equipped with filtration [14, 20]. The decoction technique includes boiling the plant samples with water for

a shorter period. With this method, it is aimed that water-soluble compounds are dissolved in hot water. However, the extract from decoction involves many water-soluble impurities and this method is not suitable for thermolabile or volatile compounds [14, 20]. Furthermore, the infusion technique is used for volatile compounds from plant samples by using a cool or boiled organic solvent with the principle of steeping for a duration of time [20].

Hydro-distillation technique has been used for bioactive compounds and essential oils from plants. In this technique, steam is used as a solvent to recover volatile or polar components from plants. There are three types of hydro distillation such as water distillation, water and steam distillation, and direct steam distillation. In the water distillation, water is brought to boiling, while hot water and steam both influence recovery of bioactive compounds in the water and steam distillation. Furthermore, direct steam is also used and injected into the plant sample. However, the hydro-distillation method has drawbacks because it may cause to loss of volatile compounds and thermal degradation of some target compounds [22].

Soxhlet extraction is a standard technique and has been used for analytical purposes and comparison of the performance of other solid-liquid extraction methods [23]. In this method, the solid samples are placed in the thimble holder over the collecting flask and under a reflux condenser. The solvent in the bottom flask is added to be heated and then it is condensed with cooling water and drops into the thimbles where the solid sample is placed. In that way, target compounds are dissolved in the warm solvent. In the end, the aqueous extract is collected in the solvent flask and then the solute is separated from the solvent using distillation. Consequently, the solute is left in the flask and fresh solvent fluids back to the solid bed [20, 23]. The procedure is continued until extraction is completed [23]. When Soxhlet extraction is compared with maceration and percolation, Soxhlet extraction is more efficient in the aspect of less solvent and time required [20]. Even though Soxhlet extraction has advantages such as no filtration requirement, enabling direct contact between solvent and solid, and being simple to handle, this method has still many disadvantageous such as long extraction time, the huge amount of solvent consumption, and high risk for thermal decomposition of target compounds [23].

Conventional techniques have still some drawbacks such as low efficiency, non-selectivity, time-consuming, high-energy requirement, and high solvent usage which are mostly high volatile organics and toxic for the human body and the environment. [24]. Due to these drawbacks, more sustainable and greener new techniques are required and searched to use in biorefineries [25].

3.2 Unconventional techniques

Conventional methods are preferred in most laboratory works due to their simplicity of use and their availability of equipment used in experiments. However, studies indicated that these methods have low efficiency for large-scale applications due to the high consumption of organic solvents in the use of maceration, percolation, and Soxhlet extraction methods. Furthermore, they cause environmental problems due to using of organic solvents and they require more time to achieve the extraction process [20]. In this regard, new extraction methods such as supercritical CO₂ extraction (SC-CO₂), microwave-assisted extraction (MAE), ultrasound-assisted extraction

(UAE), enzyme assisted extraction (EAE), pressurized fluid extraction (PFE), or even a combination of these approaches have been developed in recent years as alternative methods to conventional methods. These methods offer eco-friendlier process conditions, reducing or no toxic solvents, reducing operational time, higher efficiency, reduced formation of derivatives, prevention of degradation, use of renewable feedstocks [19]. In the following sections, non-conventional extraction methods are explained.

3.2.1 Supercritical CO₂ extraction

Supercritical carbon dioxide CO₂ (SC-CO₂), and other supercritical fluids (SCFs) have become an alternative solution to conventional industrial solvents. SCFs technology has been developed for many industrial applications in many processing technics of food, pharmaceuticals, flavors, and chemicals [26].

A fluid becomes supercritical when pressure and temperature are applied higher than its critical points. Therefore, supercritical fluid has some properties between gas and liquid as well. For example, supercritical density is similar to a liquid while its viscosity is similar to a gas. Due to its different physical and chemical properties, supercritical fluid extraction has many advantages over other extraction methods. For instance, supercritical fluids have better transport properties than liquids, thus they can diffuse easily through the solid material which helps to extract in high yield due to their low viscosity, high solvating power, and relatively high diffusivity [27]. Furthermore, the density of the supercritical fluid can be adjusted by changing temperature and pressure and it is also one of the advantages of this method because the density is directly related to the solubility [28]. The density increases with increasing pressure at constant temperature and thus solvating power increases as well while the density decreases with increasing temperature at constant pressure and then solvating power decreases as well. The supercritical fluid extraction is an effective technology to separate valuable compounds from plant material. This method can be an alternative to conventional organic solvent extraction methods because in this method high pressure is used and thus, the extraction process is achieved at a lower temperature which protects quality of the extract [29]. The aim of using this method is to modify the density of solvent to a large extent by using supercritical fluid properties and to adjust solvent properties in the extraction by changing either the applied pressure or temperature. Many solvents are used in supercritical extraction methods such as carbon dioxide, methanol, ethanol, n-butanol, ammonia, water, acetone, cyclohexane, and iso-propanol [5, 28, 30]. Lipids, proteins, nucleotides, saccharides, and other value-added compounds such as fatty acids, essential oils, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and carotenoids can be obtained by adjusting process parameters from varying options of SCFs [21, 31, 32]. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is generally used for super critical fluid extraction due to its properties such as being non-toxic, non-flammable, easy to handle and it has a critical temperature and pressure of 31.3°C and 7.4MPa, respectively. Despite that, this method has limitations such as lack of polarity and thus lack of capacity for specific solvent-solute interactions. For example, the solubility of many non-volatile compounds is very less in supercritical CO₂ due to polarity. Therefore, many investigations have been shown that there is a possibility to increase solvating power of CO₂ by using

small amounts of highly polar cosolvents [33]. Another limitation of this technique is that not enough information data exist on bio-molecules and thus prediction of phase behavior becomes difficult and uncertain [31]. Besides this, the selection of co-solvent is very important because the selected cosolvent should increase solubility, and should have high purity, and convenient physical/chemical properties according to the process to be applied. For example, the selected co-solvent has to be a non-toxic for pharmaceutical applications [30]. Icen et al. [34] carried out the experiment of the supercritical CO₂ extraction with ethanol as cosolvent on caffeine extraction from tea stalks and they reported that the mass transfer coefficient with ethanol is increased by 2.4 times related to the coefficient without ethanol. Due to the increasing mass transfer coefficient, mass transfer resistance decreases and extraction time is reduced which enables the saving the energy and carbon dioxide usage in the industrial applications. Bitencourt et al. [34] studied the solubility of caffeic acid to see the cosolvent effect in pure SC-CO₂ and with ethanol. The results showed that using 10.2 mol% ethanol in SC-CO₂ at 313 K and 20 MPa increased caffeic acid solubility 30,000 times.

Every SFE technology has a semi-continuous reactor design where biomass is placed in the extractive reactor and SC-CO₂ flows continuously through [21]. SC-CO₂ extraction system consist of a solvent feed system of CO₂, a high-pressure pump or compressor, which enables the CO₂ to flow through the system, a modifier pump where cosolvent is used if necessary, an extraction cell or extraction column, and separation column, in which the extract is collected and the solvent depressurized, a wet gas flow meter [27, 28, 32, 35]. The liquid is pumped into a heated extraction cell to become supercritical conditions and the critical fluid is controlled by a valve. To cool the CO₂, heat exchangers are used at the inlet and outlet of the pump [36]. Then it passes into the extraction vessel in which it diffuses into the solid matrix and dissolves extractable compounds. Eventually, the SC-CO₂ and the extract pass through separator where an expansion valve located on the lower side, and the pressure of CO₂ is reduced by the outlet valve till the ambient pressure [36]. Then, the extract is collected in the collection flask and CO₂ in the gas phase passes through a flow meter to control and record its flow, then it is released to environment or it is recycled [32]. However, the recycling of CO₂ should be provided to increase the process efficiency in economic and environmental aspects. Two operation models can be used in SFE systems selective extraction or selective separation [37]. Sequential separation, which includes multiple reactors in series, is used to achieve the selective of target compounds [28]. The extraction cell or the column and the separators have commonly an independent control of temperature and pressure by thermal couples and manometers [35]. Hence, different compounds can be obtained on each separator depending on their solubility in the supercritical fluid by applying separators in series. Another operation model is sequential extraction, which consists of multiple extraction vessels in series, to improve the yield of target compounds [28].

The large scale of SCFs technology has been first used in Germany in the food industry for the decaffeination of green coffee beans [38]. SFE technology is used in many industrial applications in tea and coffee decaffeination extraction of hop oleoresin, fatty acid refining, extraction of essential oils and flavors from natural sources with applications in the cosmetics, functional foods, and

pharmaceutical industries [37]. United States, France, Italy, China, and South Korea use this technology for pharmaceutical products from plant material, while India uses it for species and scents extraction and supercritical chromatography is applied for nutraceuticals in Spain and England. One of the biggest plants of SFE technologies in the world is operated in the United States for paints manufacturing using oils of vegetable matrix [37].

Effective parameters such as temperature, pressure, cosolvent concentration, extraction time and particle size play an important role in the efficiency of SFE technology [39]. Pressure and temperature have both effects on density, viscosity and diffusivity in the SFE technique. Higher temperature provides higher diffusivity and causes decreased in density which increases solvating power of the solvent. However, decreasing temperature results in a decrease in vapor pressure of solutes and increased density, thus the solubility of solutes is increased. This phenomenon is called as crossover effect and this has an effect on single target compounds, not on a complex mixture of extracts [28, 40]. Also, increasing pressure result in an increase in fluid density and increased solubility of the solute. However, too much-increased pressure may lead to the extraction of undesired compounds, reduce the diffusivity of the SCF solvent and thus cause reducing the solute dissolution [28]. For example, Pilavtepe et. al [41] investigated the effect of temperature and pressure on phenolic compounds from *Zostera marina* residues at various temperatures and pressures. The result of their investigations showed that recovery of phenolic compound increased from 57.34 to 77.22 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry feed with a flow rate of 15 g min^{-1} CO₂ with %20 ethanol as co-solvent at 35.15 K when pressure was increased from 15 MPa to 25 MPa. However, the outcome of their investigations with increasing pressure from 25 MPa to 35MPa resulted in decreased concentrations of phenolics. Also, their results showed that amounts of total phenolic acids were increased from 36.00 to 72.22 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ at 25 MPa when the temperature was increased from 323.15 K to 353.3 K [41]. Another study was made by Döker et. al [42] to see the effect of temperature and pressure on β -carotene from apricot bagasse. Their results revealed that the yield of β -carotene is increased almost 1,5-fold higher when the temperature was increased from 313 K to 333 K. Furthermore, the concentration of β -carotene was improved from 0,019 kg m^{-3} to 0,0303 kg m^{-3} by increasing pressure from 40.5 MPa to 50.7 MPa at 333 K [42]. Another study was carried out by Aladic et. al on seed oil from Hemp seeds [43], the outcome of investigations showed that increasing pressure had no effect on fatty acids concentrations obtained from extracts whereas increasing pressure has an effect on tocopherol obtained from extracts [43]. Therefore, the SFE technique is a selective method by adjusting pressure and temperature. Hence, temperature and pressure should be adjusted regarding the properties of the target compound and its behavior in SFE.

Some studies have been carried out to see the effect of particle size on extraction efficiency in SFE. For example, Kehili et.al. [44] studied the size effect of tomato peels on oleoresin extraction by using different particle sizes as grounded tomato peels of 0.3 mm size and unground tomato peels of 1 mm size with a CO₂ flow rate of 4g/min for 105 min at 50°C and 400 bar. The results showed that the yield of oleoresin was increased by reducing particles sizes [44]. Reducing the particle size increases the mass transfer rate by reducing the diffusion path between the

solute and solvent, thus the yield of the target compound is increased [39]. Another study was carried out by Soh et.al. [40] on Patchouli oil from Patchouli leaves with different particle sizes in the range between 0.3- 0.6 mm, 0 - 0.15 mm, and 0.84 -1.19 mm at 12 MPa, 313 K, with a CO₂ flow rate of 0.1667 g/s. The results indicated that the yield of Patchouli was increased when the particle size was reduced from 0.84-1.19 mm to 0.3-0.6 mm. Nevertheless, when particle size was reduced from 0.3-0.6 mm to 0-0.15 mm, the yield was decreased [40]. Therefore, extremely small particles can cause non-homogeneous fluid flow through the bed and agglomerate the fine particles which leads to longer diffusion paths and decreased mass transfer rate [40].

Due to the lack of polarity of SC-CO₂, co-solvents are required for polar compounds to be extracted. Therefore, many investigations have been made in the literature to see the effect of co-solvents in the SC-CO₂ technique. For example, Radzali et. al. [45] investigated the effect of co-solvents on phenolic compounds from *Labisia pumilia* by using ethanol, water, methanol, as well as aqueous solutions of ethanol-water and methanol-water (50% and 70% v/v) at 200 bar and 60°C. Results of the study indicated that the highest yield of targeted phenolic compounds such as gallic acid, methyl gallate, and caffeic acid was obtained by using 70% ethanol-water, even though 50% ethanol-water solvent gave the highest total phenolic compounds. Therefore, the polarity of single target compounds is important in the selection of co-solvent and in some cases, the use of co-solvent may reduce the targeted extraction of bioactivities, even if the total yield of the extract is increased [28, 45].

3.2.2 Microwave assisted extraction

Microwave assisted extraction technique has gained much interest in recent years to extract valuable compounds from plant materials due to the high demand for alternative green technologies. This technique can be transferred from laboratory scale to industrial scale since it can be adapted on a small or large volume [46]. The MAE method has advantages over other conventional methods such as less extraction time, less solvent usage, and low equipment cost [47–50]. Using the MAE technique many compounds such as aromas, antioxidants, colors, bio-phenols, and other secondary and primary metabolites have been efficiently extracted from different plant materials [51]. Microwaves are electromagnetic waves with a range of 300 MHz to 300 GHz corresponding wavelengths of 1m to 1 cm and microwave radiation leads to molecular motion by migration of ions and rotation of dipoles. [48]. In industrial applications in the range of 915 MHz and 2,450 MHz frequencies are used [52]. In this method sample/solvent is heated to ease and speed up the extraction of the analyte. The reason for using the microwave for heating is that it has a direct effect on the molecules of the sample and heats the solution directly, whereas in conventional methods a certain time is needed to heat the vessel before heating the solution. These speeds up the heating and thus extraction time is reduced. The extraction takes place due to changes in cell structure as a result of electromagnetic waves effects [53]. Energy transfer has two mechanisms in the microwave heating process; Ionic conduction and dipole rotation.

Ionic conduction occurs when an electromagnetic field is applied. The direction of ions changes many times when the field changes sign, then it causes a collision between molecules therefore the resistance of the solution to this

flow of ions and collision between molecules cause friction and consequently heat the solution [54]. Moreover, solvent penetration into the matrix is increased due to the migration of dissolved ions and hence solvation of the target compound is facilitated. The dipole rotation is an alternative movement of polar molecules which have dipole moments that can occur permanently or by the electric field and they try to line up with the electric field [55]. Thermal energy is released due to thermal disorder. This dipole rotation causes the breakdown of hydrogen bonds. The higher viscosity of the medium reduces this mechanism by affecting molecular rotation because when viscosity increases, the dissipation factor decreases, and thus microwave energy cannot be well absorbed [46, 56]. To generate heat in the sample in the MAE process, the presence of a dielectric compound is required [55]. Thus, only selective and targeted compounds can be heated depending on their dielectric constants [57]. The generated heat energy is described from the dissipation factor equation ($\tan\delta$) which is the ratio of sample dielectric loss (ϵ'') to dielectric constant(ϵ') [58]. The dielectric constant of the sample is the ability to absorb microwave energy and the loss factor indicates the ability to transform microwave radiation into heat. The higher the dissipation factor, the higher the heat energy will be [46]. Therefore, the efficiency of microwave energy depends on the solid sample and solvent properties.

Microwave radiation energy heats up the solute-solvent mixture and the diffusivity of solvent to the target compound is increased by the generated heat. The disruption of hydrogen bonds in the material increases the penetrating efficiency of solvent into the material, and thus target compounds can easily dissolve into the extraction fluid [20]. The working principle of the MAE method is different from the conventional method because the mass transfer and heat transfer occur from inside to outside in the same direction while heat transfer in conventional methods occurs from outside to the inside of the material [53]. The extraction heating process can happen by three mechanisms; (1) the sample can be immersed in a single solvent or mixture of solvents that absorb microwave energy highly; (2) the sample can be extracted in combined solvent mixtures with high and low dielectric losses in different proportions; (3) the sample can have high water content and can be extracted with a microwave transparent solvent that enables absorption by polar reactants [55]. Generally, the polar solvent is chosen which has a high dielectric constant, in that way, the microwave energy can be more absorbed. However, due to prevent the degradation of thermolabile components, in some cases, only the solid sample can be heated by microwave energy, and thus solute can be released in the cold solvent [55]. This principle in the MAE method is explained as ; (1) the irradiation of heat from the microwave is transferred into solid material through microwave transparent solvent; (2) the moisture in solid material evaporates and causes high vapor pressure; (3) this vapor pressure ruptures the cell of the material; (4) the high-value compounds are transferred from solid into non-absorbing solvent due to breakage of cell structure in the material [53].

Two types of MAE systems are commercially available; (1) closed extraction vessels under controlled pressure and temperature or named pressurized MAE (PMAE); (2) open vessels at atmospheric pressure or named focused MAE (FMAE) [59]. The temperature can be modified by applying pressure in closed vessels, while the temperature depends on the boiling point of the solvent

at atmospheric pressure [55]. In the closed MAE technique, high pressure and temperature are controlled during the process and provide fast, efficient extraction, and less solvent [60]. However, a closed system may lead to losses of volatile compounds. In contrast to closed systems, open systems can be more suitable for thermolabile compounds. Open systems are operated under ambient conditions and overcome safety issues that occur in closed systems. In this system, only part of the vessel is connected to microwave radiation, and the upper part of the vessel is connected to a reflux unit to condense any vaporized solvent [57].

The MAE technique has advantages and disadvantages compared to the other techniques. One of the big advantages is reducing the time of extraction and the use of solvents [61]. Furthermore, this technique enables high target compound and selectivity of the heating process due to using a non-contact heat source [55, 59, 61]. The MAE has a moderate cost of equipment set up and it makes the MAE technique feasible and cheaper than other unconventional methods such as SFE or PLE in the economic aspect [57]. On the other hand, this method has limitations as well. One of the big limitations is that solid residue remains in the extractor, then it is required to remove this solid residue by using any other additional process such as filtration or centrifugation. Moreover, this method is not suitable for heat-sensitive compounds due to increased temperature during the process [50]. In addition, this method is not efficient for non-polar target compounds by using non-polar solvents or volatile compounds [50]. Non-polar solvents have a poor ability to absorb microwave energy and convert it to heat energy. However, this limitation can be overcome by using other polar modifiers such as water into non-polar solvents in order to increase the ability to absorb microwave energy. Another drawback of the MAE technique it requires time for cooling and cleaning after the extraction is done, this may cause losing extracted active compounds [57].

The MAE technique ensures higher extraction yields and efficiency at both laboratory and industrial scale by reducing energy and solvent consumption with compare to other conventional methods. The industrial application of the MAE technique has been successfully achieved in cosmetic and food production due to its economic and environmental advantages [49, 62]. MAE technique has been used on a commercial scale and applied for isolating essential oils, fats, and oils [50]. Some commercial microwave systems from companies such as Milestone, CEM, and Sineo are used in industrial applications and offer high throughput extraction vessels, pressurized systems, temperature control and monitoring, vessel cooling systems, and overhead condensing unit [63].

The main parameters affecting the performance of the MAE technique are properties of the solvent and solid material, microwave power, exposure time, solvent volume, and temperature [60].

Li et al. [64] studied the effect of microwave power by using 300, 400, 500, 600, 700, and 800 W on the extraction of antioxidants from the fruit *Gordonia axillaris* under the conditions of ethanol concentration of 40%, solvent to solid ratio 20 mL/g, extraction time of 75 min and extraction temperature of 40 °C. According to their results, the Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) value increased with the microwave power increasing from 300 to 400 W and reached the highest value at 400 W as 190.33±6.57 (µmolTrolox/gDW). However, when microwave power continued to increase, the TEAC value

decreased. According to their study and the other studies in the literature [65, 66], high microwave power may lead to less extraction yield of target compounds due to the degradation of thermal sensible compounds, even though microwave power rapids the solvent's movement, and cell rupture, and the diffusion of extractives into the solvent [57, 64].

Xia et al. [65] investigated the effect of time on the extraction of Oxymatrine from the *Sophora flavescens* plant, under the conditions of 60 % ethanol with a ratio of liquid to solid material of 20:1, at 50°C with microwave irradiation of 500 W. The results of their study revealed that the yield of oxymatrine increased from 0 to 10 min, and then the yield decreased after 10 min. In their study, maximum yield was obtained at 10 min as 14.37±0.48 mg/g. Therefore, their and other investigations in literature [52, 57, 66] indicated microwave accelerates the extraction of target compounds but after a long time, it causes some target compounds to be degraded.

Liaid et al. [67] studied the effect of temperature between 50 and 175°C on the stability of phenolic compounds. Their study concluded that all the phenolic compounds were stable up to 100°C and an increase in temperature caused significant degradation of epicatechin, resveratrol, and myricetin. Similar observations were made by Li et al. [64] where the antioxidant capacity of the extract increased from 30 to 40 °C, and a further increase in temperature from 40 to 70 °C led to a decrease in antioxidant capacity. Their investigations [64, 67] might explain that higher temperatures cause some degradation of thermolabile compounds even though high temperature increases the diffusivity and solubility of compounds.

3.2.3 Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE)

Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) is an effective technique that uses ultrasound waves with frequencies between 20 kHz and 100 MHz [68]. Polyphenols, carotenoids, and nutraceuticals such as essential oils and lipids have been extracted by using the UAE technique [23, 69]. The UAE is considered a green technique and has many advantages over other conventional methods such as less use of solvent, short extraction time, easy equipment, low cost for equipment installation, and less environmental impact [70]. The principle of the UAE is based on the cavitation phenomenon. During the UAE cavitation bubbles are produced by acoustic cavitation and thus the solute easily diffuses from solid material due to the breaking of plant cell walls [71, 72]. The cavitation induces a series of compressions and rarefactions in the liquid medium which increases the distance between molecules, creates space among them, and causes pressure changes and the formation of bubbles [73, 74]. Then, the implosion of cavitation bubbles near a solid surface causes a series of micro-jetting effects which leads to generating shockwaves due to erosion, fragmentations, or shear forces [70]. Furthermore, the implosion of cavitation bubbles in a liquid medium causes macro turbulences. The UAE technique has a mechanical effect and it increases the penetration of solvent into the solid material by shock waves and hydrodynamic force toward the solid surface [75]. As a result of mechanical effects of ultrasound-induced cavitation, such as heat and pressure differentials, shock waves, shear forces, micro-jetting, micro-mixing, and macro-turbulences intensify the penetration of the solvent into the cell interior and enhances the mass transfer between cell and solvent so that the intercellular materials are transferred into the solvent.

This method can be combined with other methods such as MAE, EAE, PLE, or SFE [73, 76]. The UAE techniques consist of a power generator, a transducer that converts electrical energy into acoustic energy by vibrating mechanically at ultrasonic frequencies, an amplifier, and a probe [73]. In the UAE process, raw material takes place in the extraction vessel, and the solvent is added at the desired temperature. After the extraction process is done, filtration is used to recover the extracted compounds [73]. Various types of components were extracted such as essential oils, carotenoids, antioxidants, flavors, etc. on the laboratory scale [77].

Reactor type and its design are important factors in the UAE technique [78]. In the laboratory and industrial applications, two types of systems are mainly used; (1) bath (ultrasonic cleaners) and (2) probes (ultrasonic horns or sonotrodes) Both ultrasound baths and ultrasound probes systems have advantages and drawbacks [70, 78, 79]. The cleaning bath is used for solid dispersion into the solvent and consists of the tank, the electronic generator which supplies electrical power to the transducer [77, 79]. In industrial applications, this system can be combined with other units for stuffing, de-stuffing, transport, washing, drying, solvent recovery, etc. [79]. This system is simple, easy to build, and has a minor implementation cost. However, this system has some drawbacks such as providing not sufficient power and thus not efficient energy transfer within the vessel containing extract [70]. Probe devices have a generator which is a source of alternating electrical frequency, transducer, and horn. In contrast to the bath systems, probe systems irradiate directly ultrasounds into the extracts and thus these systems provide more efficient in irradiating the reaction medium [70]. This system provides up to 100 times higher ultrasound energy than bath systems. In the extraction process, the probe is immersed into the vessel with raw material, then direct sonication occurs. Ultrasound energy transmitted to the medium can be regulated by using different boosters in industrial probes [79]. Probes provide more power and higher energy is transmitted to the medium than the bath system. However, some volatile compounds can be lost due to degassing effect in probe systems. Furthermore, generated heat by the effect of the sonication can change the characteristics of the medium, therefore cooling of sonication vessel is required and control of the sonication must be provided in order to prevent the degradation of bioactive compounds [79]. In probe systems, optimization of variables such as amplitude, time, and pressure for the extraction is possible to protect the structure of value-added compounds by controlling operating temperature [70]. Furthermore, regarding laboratory investigations, the probe type system showed more efficiency for the extraction of phenolic compounds and antioxidants from various plants showed better extraction yield and higher antioxidant capacity of extracts than the bath type system [78]. Both probe and bath systems are used in industrial depending on the process application usually from 30 to 1000 L volume and powers ranging from 500 to 16,000 W with pump systems which are used for filling the ultrasonic bath, stirring the mixture, and emptying tanks. [77, 79]. Although the batch mode is used in laboratory investigations, the continuous flow mode is available for industrial applications.

The UAE technique has many advantages such as effective mixing capability, higher yield, low operation temperature, faster extraction kinetics, and the extraction of heat-sensitive compounds with minimal damage lower

equipment costs than other nonconventional methods such as MAE and SFE [23, 61, 78]. Moreover, in the UAE technique, any solvents can be used for the extraction of various natural compounds like Soxhlet extraction [23]. However, this technique has limitations as well. The major challenge is wave attenuation in the dispersed phase and a decline in transmission of the ultrasound waves away from the vicinity of the generator due to the non-uniformity of the dispersed phase [23, 50, 78].

Extraction time, temperature, ultrasonic power, frequency, solvent type, the ratio of solid to solvent, and particle size affect the extraction process in the UAE technique [72, 79]. For example, Cui et al. [80] investigated the effect of ultrasound power on the extraction of polysaccharides from *Volvariella volvacea* (straw mushroom). They set the parameters as ultrasound frequency of 20 kHz, extraction temperature of 50°C, extraction time of 20 min, and liquid/material ratio of 20:1 by changing ultrasound power in the range from 60 W to 240 W. Their results indicated that the increase of ultrasound power from 60 W to 210 W improved the polysaccharide yield from 4.82% to 7.63%. In spite of that, a further increase of power to 240 W caused to decrease in the yield of polysaccharides to 7.59%. Another study was carried out by Moradi et al. [81] to see the effect of ultrasound frequency on oil extraction from the sunflower. Their experimental set conditions for two different frequencies (25 kHz and 40 kHz) were as follows; n-hexane as the solvent, solid-to-solvent ratio 1:12, average particle size $250 \pm 12 \mu\text{m}$, temperature 20°C, and extraction time 2 h. As a result of their study, the extraction yield of oil was higher at 24 kHz than the yield of oil at 40 kHz. According to Moradi et. al [81], this could be explained that cavitation intensity was greater at 24 kHz than at 40 kHz because the cavitation bubbles had a long time to grow and collapse under ultrasonic oscillation with lower frequency, which helped the intensification of the cavitation effect.

Another investigation was made by Altemimi et al. [82] to clarify the effects of different combinations of ultrasonic water bath factors tested on phenolic compound yield from spinach including frequency (37 and 80 kHz), exposure time (5,10,15,20,25 and 30 min), temperature (30,40 and 50°C), and ultrasonic power (30%,50%, and 70%). The best results were obtained as total phenol $33.96 \pm 11.30 \text{ mg gallic acid/g DW}$ and flavonoids $27.37 \pm 11.85 \text{ mg/g DW}$ under conditions ultrasonic frequency of 37 kHz, extraction time of 30 min, reaction temperature of 40°C, and ultrasonic power of %50. According to the results of Altemimi et al., temperature and power had remarkable effects on other variables. For example, the 40 °C temperature gave the highest yield at 37 kHz and 80 kHz with the ultrasound power of 50%. The power setting of 50% provided a significantly higher yield of phenolic compounds compared to the power settings of 30% and 70% at 40°C and in both frequencies. Furthermore, polyphenol extraction from spinach by the UAE technique showed high antioxidant capacity, and the UAE method was strongly recommended by Altemimi et al. for extraction of bioactive compounds from plant materials.

3.2.4 Enzyme assisted extraction (EAE)

EAE technique uses special enzymes to extract bioactive compounds by disrupting the cell wall of the material to improve extraction yield. Due to difficulties of extraction for some bioactive compounds such as phytochemicals, lipids, or proteins from the cell structure

of plant material, enzymes are used for pre-treatment to get better yield and higher quality of bioingredients [83, 84]. Enzymes have been used to extract many phenolic compounds, including flavonoids and anthocyanidins [85]. Several types of enzymes are used such as cellulase, pectinase, and hemicellulose and enzymes can be derived from bacteria, fungi, animal organs, or vegetables/fruits [83, 86–88]. The working principle of the EAE method is that enzymes hydrolyze the plant cell walls and thus intracellular components are released from the cell under suitable conditions for the specific enzymes [89].

Enzymes are used on an industrial scale as catalysts in the applications and one of the advantages in the application of industrial scale is less organic solvent usage in the aspect of environmental effect [90]. The main aim of enzymes usually used for plant-based drinks production and syrups for saccharification, decreased viscosity, higher yield and low toxicity in the food industry. For example, pectinases are used in the fruit juice industry due to their effectiveness, higher juice yield, filterability, lower viscosity, and increased transparency [85]. The main advantages of enzyme pre-treatment are reducing the usage of solvent with increased yield, quality, and preservation of product [84, 90]. Enzymes are water-soluble, non-toxic, and easily biodegradable and they can be operated at mild conditions of pH, temperature, and pressure [91]. The limitation of this technique is the cost and availability of enzymes for large volumes on the industrial scale [84, 85, 89, 90]. However, balancing the concentration of enzyme preparations, tailor-made enzyme preparations for specific reactions, and using crude enzyme preparations in commercial applications can help to overcome this limitation [84, 89]. Even the high cost of enzymes for large-scale applications can be covered by the high cost of value-added compounds in the market [84, 90]. On the other hand, if the enzyme lifetime is prolonged, the cost can be reduced correspondingly [90]. Furthermore, enzymes usage and dosage due to regulations for the extracted compounds can be a limiting factor. Therefore, the stability and repeatability of enzymes and their interaction with other food and plant ingredients should be investigated because the properties of each plant material changes within origin, cultivation, growing, harvesting, and storage conditions [85]. Another limitation of this technique is purification methods because purification of processing is more difficult and complex than other conventional methods [90].

Plant matrix, depending on solute properties and location, optimum conditions such as pH, temperature, solid to solvent ratio, and incubation time which vary from enzyme to enzyme affect the efficiency of EAE [91]. For example, a study was carried out by Zhao et al. [92] to determine optimal conditions for extraction of polysaccharides from *Lentinus edodes* (edible and medicinal mushrooms) by using cellulase, papain, and pectinase enzymes. Their study revealed that the highest polysaccharides yield of 15.65 % was obtained with the extraction of 54°C, pH 5.0, enzymatic treatment time of 93 min, and solid to liquid ratio of 1/29.1 ml/g. They observed that the pH value has a significant effect on target compounds in the EAE and in their experiment different pH values of between 3.0 and 7.0 were evaluated. Their results indicated that the highest yield was achieved with pH 5.0 and a further increase of pH decreased the yield. They explained this phenomenon that the spatial structure of the enzymes was changing by pH value and thus enzyme conformation and enzymatic activity were

changed. Furthermore, they observed the same results by operating different temperatures of between 30°C and 70°C. The yield was increased with the temperature from 30°C and 50 °C, a further increase in temperature led to a decrease in the yield. Their interpretation of this phenomenon was that enzymes have a maximal hydrolyzing activity at their optimum temperature and a further increase in temperature affects highly enzyme activity. Another reason was explained by the thermal degradation of polysaccharides at higher temperatures [92].

Another study was performed by Huy et al. [93] on the extraction yield of Triterpenoid Saponins from *Pseuderanthemum palatiferum* (herb) by using Viscozyme enzyme in EAE. They obtained the Saponins yield of 64.19% and higher than the Soxhlet extraction method which enabled the yield of 14.76%. In this study, the effect of enzyme concentration was studied. In the experiment, enzyme concentration varied from 2.5 to 15.0 µL/g with other parameters kept constant as solid to water ratio of 1/12.5 g/ml, the temperature of 50°C, and the extraction time of 120 min. Their results indicated that the highest yield of total Saponins of 1.970 mg/g was achieved with the enzyme concentration of 7.5 µL/g. A decrease in bioactivities was observed after the enzyme concentration was increased. Huy et al. explained that the activity of Viscozyme was reduced due to hydrolyze of protein which can be caused by protease pseuderrant in due to the release of the high concentration of the enzyme [93].

3.2.5 Pressurized fluid extraction (PFE)

Pressurized fluid extraction is an advanced technique and has advantages over conventional extraction methods. PLE uses solvent at high temperature (usually up to 200°C) and pressure (usually up to 200 bar) beyond their critical point, in which the solvent remains in the liquid form during the extraction process [94–96]. The PFE technique is also known as accelerated solvent extraction (ASE), pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), pressurized hot extraction solvent extraction (PHSE), high-pressure solvent extraction (HPSE), high-pressure high-temperature extraction ((HPHTSE), and subcritical solvent extraction (SSE) [94]. Due to high temperature and pressure, physicochemical properties of solvent are changed such as viscosity, surface tension, and solvating power [94, 96]. When the temperature is increased, viscosity and solvent surface tension are decreased, and this provides higher diffusivity of solvent into the solid material. Furthermore, due to the high temperature, solvating power of the solvent is increased, and in this way the solubility of the target compound in the solvent is increased than solubility at ambient conditions [97]. Hence, the PFE method provides less extraction time, less organic solvent usage, and higher yield compared to conventional methods. Furthermore, the PFE system equipment allows running the process automatically which enables quality control, less labor, and reproducibility [94, 98]. In the PFE technique ethanol, ethyl acetate, ethyl lactate, and water are mostly used as solvents [94]. However, among these solvents water is considered the most environmentally friendly, cheapest, and ideal solvent for the bioactive compounds in the pharmaceutical and food industry [94, 99, 100].

The equipment of the PLE technique is simple and easy to construct. The set-up of equipment changes regarding extraction mode as either dynamic, static, or dynamic static. However, typical instrumentation has a

solvent reservoir, a pump, an oven to heat the extraction cell, different valves and restrictors, and a collecting vial [94, 101, 102]. The solvent reservoir is connected with the high-pressure pump, which pumps the solvent into the cell and pumps the extract out from the extraction cell when the extraction is done. For example, in the case of using water as a solvent, water should be oxygen-free, which can be achieved with degassing by ultrasound or by helium purge, to prevent oxidation of bioactive compounds and cavitation in the pump [101]. The solid material is placed in the extraction cell, which is heated by the oven, and the extraction occurs in the extraction cell [102]. The oven should have valves to keep the extraction conditions stable and control the extraction pressure. At the end of the extraction, the extract is collected in the collecting vial, while hot solvent passes through the condenser and is taken out from the condenser [94, 101, 102].

As mentioned above, different modes of extraction are used as either, dynamic, static, or a combination of both, namely static dynamic [103]. The dynamic mode is a continuous extraction process, the solvent is continuously fed into the extractor with a pump, while solid material and solvent are treated for a specific time at constant temperature and pressure in the static mode [94, 103]. The static mode has less efficiency than the dynamic mode because the dynamic mode enables the automation of the whole process with modifications of the process parameters and achieves selectively continuous extraction [104]. However, in many cases, both static and dynamic modes are used to increase yield and reduce the extraction time and solvent usage.

Most studies on bioactive compounds extraction with subcritical water extraction techniques have been studied at laboratory scale and pilot scale [50, 103, 105]. Results of pilot-scale studies have shown that the development of industrial-scale of subcritical water extraction technique is possible [103]. Furthermore, subcritical water extraction (SWE) is used for breaking down cellulose, and hemicellulose biopolymers into simple sugars and small molecules for downstream fermentation or gasification. The high density of water at high temperatures provides the hydrolysis reaction for the conversion of biomass into simple sugars. The SWE has a high potential for the valorization of biomass to high value-added compounds, especially for the liquefaction of protein-rich biomasses. The SWE technique can enhance the extraction and decomposition of proteins and their constituent amino acids. After the extraction step, the purification step is required to achieve commercially efficient amino acids and proteins [106]. The main applications of SWE can be summarized that it has been used in the extraction of bioactive compounds from many food matrixes such as flavonoids from mandarin [107], anthocyanins, pectin, galotannins, polyphenols from different fruits and herbs, and essential oils as well as its application in the hydrolysis of biopolymers, proteins and in the release of amino acids from different sources [108]. The main advantage of SWE is that fewer pretreatments are required such as drying or grinding compared to acid, alkali, and enzyme hydrolysis. Moreover, in the SWE less waste and degradation products are generated and providing shorter extraction time and less corrosion problems [109].

There are some industrial applications of the SWE technique for the valorization of different biomasses. For example, the Catliq technology has been developed by the Danish Company and the scale-up was carried out to produce green oil from wet low-value feeds such as

sludge, algae, manure, and residues from food production in a pilot plant with a 30L/h continuous process by using two catalysts at subcritical conditions ranging from 280 to 350°C and from 22.5 to 25.0 MPa [106, 110]. Also, another scale-up is performed by the company Renmatrix to convert cellulose into cellulosic sugar by using water under subcritical conditions. Moreover, the Conagra Butterball Co., in the USA performed the scale-up process of 250 tons/day of turkey offal and fats [106, 110].

The PLE technique has many advantages such as less extraction time, high yield, reproducibility, high solvating power, high diffusivity, and high mass transfer. Especially among PLE techniques, subcritical water extraction is suitable for value-added compounds from plant materials such as essential oils, tannins, lignans, phenolic acids, lactones, and flavonoids [111]. Subcritical water extraction has many advantages such as low cost, rapid, and environmentally friendly. Furthermore, extraction of polar, moderately polar, and nonpolar compounds can be achieved by modifying parameters such as temperature, pressure, and co-solvent. In contrast to SC-CO₂, subcritical water extraction can extract compounds from moderately polar to heavy molecular weight in plants, while SC-CO₂ can be used for non-polar compounds and light components in plant materials and has a poor extraction yield of flavonoids, lignans, and other related polyphenolic compounds [111]. Additionally, subcritical water extraction equipment is much simpler and cheaper than the equipment of SC-CO₂ [105, 111]. However, the PLE technique has some drawbacks in that it can lead to thermal degradation for thermolabile compounds in the extracts at high temperatures and pressure. Besides this, cleaning is required for equipment of the PLE technique after the extraction process is done [50, 105].

In the PLE different parameters can be optimized to achieve the highest recoveries of value-added compounds which have a significant effect on the yield of recoveries. The most important parameters are the temperature, pressure, solvent flow rate, static time, solid to solvent ratio, particle size, and the number of cycles [94, 95, 97]. A study was performed by Haghghi et al. [100] on the extraction of essential oil from *Z. multiflora* leaves by using subcritical water extraction. Their study showed that a total essential oil yield of 2.58% (w/w) based on dry weight was obtained at most by using subcritical water extraction whereas the yield of 1.5 in hydrodistillation extraction and the yield of 2.21% in Soxhlet extraction was obtained. Furthermore, they examined the effect of temperature on essential oils with the temperature between 125 and 175°C. Their results revealed that the highest amount of thymol and carvacrol of essential oils were obtained with an increase in temperature up to 150°C. With a further increase at 175°C, the yield of essential oils reduced, and a burning smell occurred in the extract. They explained that degradation of some compounds at higher temperatures might have occurred and they determined the optimal temperature of 150°C [100].

Another optimization study was carried out by Hironnant et al. [98] to determine the solvent on extraction efficiency of rosmarinic acid, and carnosic acid from rosmarin leaves. They evaluated the ethanol/water ratio of 0,20,40,60,80, and 100% (g/g) in PLE. The evaluation resulted that rosmarinic acid was extracted at low ethanol percentages of 0 and 20% but no carnosic acid which was obtained from %40 ethanol percentage. Moreover, the outcome of the study showed that %80 ethanol percentage maximized rosmarinic acid and carnosic acid yields of

10.13±0.02 mg rosmarinic acid/rosemary and 20.6±0.4 mg carnosic acid/rosemary. They explained that rosmarinic acid is a caffeic ester and relatively polar, as ethanol and thus it dissolves better in high ethanol percentages. Also, carnosic acid is relatively lipophilic, and still soluble in intermediate polarity solvents such as ethanol or acetone [98].

4 COMPARISONS OF METHODS

Table I and Table II are established to make a comparison between novel extraction methods for value-added compounds. In Table I, the benefits and limitations of the unconventional methods (SC-CO₂, MAE, UAE, EAE, and PLE) are listed to have a general overview of the techniques. In Table II, the yield of different target compounds from various biomasses is compared in different methods within the process's parameters applied. Additionally, it is aimed to have a general overview of the methods with important process parameters such as temperature, pressure, extraction time, and solid to solvent ratio. As can be seen from Table II, unconventional

methods provide usually a higher yield of target compounds than conventional methods. The conventional methods are time-consuming and require a high amount of solvent. For example, according to investigations in the literature, maceration and Soxhlet extraction methods require a long time for the extraction of phenolic compounds, carotenes, flavonoids, and protein extraction in contrast to MAE, UAE, SC-CO₂, and SWE [64, 114–116]. To choose an appropriate method among the unconventional methods, the properties of target compounds and solid matrices are important. For instance, the amount of total phenolic compounds from the pumpkin peel extract was higher in SC-CO₂ while carotenoids were extracted at most in SWE [116]. According to investigations in the literature, the SWE technique for protein extraction [114], UAE and MAE [64, 117] for phenolic compounds, and SC-CO₂ [117] for tocopherols provided convincing amounts.

In some cases, a combination of methods might be required to improve the yield when a single method is not enough to extract the desired amount of the target compound. Hence, the integration of the methods may increase the efficiency of the extraction process [20, 73].

Table I: Benefits and drawbacks of the unconventional extraction methods

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
SC-CO ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non toxicity, non-flammable [31] • High diffusivity, higher mass transfer [31] • Higher extraction rate, less extraction time [61, 112] • Conservation of thermolabile compounds due to low critical temperature of CO₂ [32, 37, 39, 61] • Selectivity for desired compound [31, 32, 61] • Possible to recycle CO₂ [37, 61] • Applications on large scale [37, 38] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investment cost • High energy consumption [31, 37, 61, 113] • Low polarity, thus it is required co-solvent for extraction of polar molecules [27, 37, 61]
MAE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less extraction time, less solvent usage [48, 50] • High extraction yield [61] • Less equipment cost [48, 50] • Stable and reproducible [57] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not suitable for heat sensitive bioactive compounds [50, 61] • Poor extraction yield for nonpolar compounds [48, 50] • Additional separation process required [50] • Clean up and cooling required [50, 57]
UAE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High extraction yield [23, 78] • Low operation temperature [23, 78] • Less equipment cost than other techniques [61] • Efficient for heat sensitive compounds [23, 61, 78] • Applicable in industrial scale [61] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of uniformity of ultrasound energy in dispersed phase [50]
EAE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using enzymes yield is increased [85, 89, 90] • High quality of product [84, 85, 89, 90] • High preservation of product [84, 90] • Less organic solvent usage [90] • Environmental friendly [90] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of enzymes on large scale [85, 89, 90] • Difficulty of availability of enzymes on large scale [85, 89, 90] • Difficulty and more complex on purification step than other techniques [90]
PLE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non toxicity, nonflammable [105] • Higher diffusivity, higher mass transfer [94, 96, 97] • Higher solvating power, less extraction time [97, 105] • Selectivity of target compounds [111] • Simple and cheap equipment [50, 105] • Possible to automation of process [50, 94, 98] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thermal degradation for thermolabile compounds [50, 105] • Clean up required after the process done [50, 105]

Table II: An overview of the extraction methods from various biomasses

Biomass source	Process parameters	Target compound	Remarks	Ref.
<i>Gordonia axillaris</i> (plant)	MAC: % 36.89 ethanol, R:1/29.56 g/ml, 24h, 25°C SOX: % 36.89 ethanol, R:1/800 g/ml, 4 h, 85°C MAE: % 36.89 ethanol, R: 1/29.56 g/ml, 71.04 min, 40°C, 400 W	Total Phenolic compounds, (TPC) MAC: 13.69 ±0.11 mg GAE/g DW SOX: 9.63 ± 0.45 mg GAE/g DW MAE: 198.16 ± 5.47 mg GAE/g DW	MAE provided the highest yield of TPC and the highest antioxidant capacity.	[64]
<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> (Medical plant)	MAC: % 50 ethanol, R:1/5 g/ml, 5-day, room temp SOX: R:1/30 g/ml, n-hexane, 8 h, SC-CO₂: 100g sample, 30 MPa, 40°C 2 kg/h flow rate of CO ₂	Umbelliferone and herniarin MAC: 4.78 ±0.15 mg umbelliferone /100 g, 45.54 ± 4.16 mg herniarin /100g SOX: 0.00 mg/100g umbelliferone, 20.22 ±2.28 mg/100g SC-CO₂: 0.33 mg/100g umbelliferone, 37.05 ±2.28 mg/100g	The highest yield was achieved by maceration because SC-CO ₂ and Hexane have a low ability to dissolve polar compounds.	[118]
<i>Amaranthus caudatus</i> (plant)	UAE: Methanol, R:1/20 g/ml, 1 h, 25°C, SC-CO₂: 5g sample, 2L/min flow rate of CO ₂ , 15min, 400atm,70°C	Tocopherols UAE: 63.7 ± 8.3 mg/kg SC-CO₂: 129.27 ± 14.8mg/kg	SC-CO ₂ ensured the highest yield in shorter time without co solvent.	[117]
<i>Sun flower</i> (plant)	SOX: n-Hexane, R: 1/40 g/ml, 10 h, 68°C UAE: n-Hexane, R:1/12, 2h, 24kHz, 280 W, 50°C	Tocopherols SOX: 620.24 ± 1.4 mg/kg UAE: 610.12 ± 2.7 mg/kg	UAE and Soxhlet had similar results but UAE provided shorter time and less solvent usage.	[81]
<i>Malpighia emarginata</i> DC. (fruit)	EAE: Water, Celluclast 1.5 L, enzyme concentration of 8.1 NCU g ⁻¹ , R:1/2 g/ml, 120 min, 50°C, UAE: Water, R:1/2 g/ml, 6 min, 450 W,50°C	Phenolics and Vitamin C EAE: 35.7% vitamin C and 9.0% phenolics UAE: 40.3% vitamin C and 12.5% phenolics	UAE provided higher phenolic content and higher antioxidant activity compared to EAE.	[119]
<i>Satureja hartensis</i> L. (summer savory, plant)	MAC: 96% ethanol, R:1/30 g/ml, 7 day, 22 °C SWE: R: 1/20 g/ml, 30 min, 40 bar, 140°C	Total phenolic compounds (TPC) Total flavonoids content (TFC) MAC: 147.21 ± 0.15 TPC mgGAE/g, 23.10±0.18 TFC mg RU/g SWE: 151.54 ± 0.85 TPC mgGAE/g, 28.42 ± 0.29 TFC mgRU/g	SWE provided higher yield of TPC and TFC in shorter time than maceration.	[115]
<i>Pseuderanthemum palatiferum</i> (Medical plant)	SOX: %70 ethanol, R:1/70 g/ml, 7 h SWE: R:1/70 g/ml, 15 min, 80 bar, 230°C HWE: R:1/25 g/ml,30 min, 80°C	Total protein (mg BSA/g) SOX: Non determined HWE: 3.21± 0.64 mg BSA/g SWE: 104.66 ± 7.63 mg BSA/g	Protein was not achieved in the Soxhlet extraction. Protein was achieved at most with SWE in a shorter time.	[114]
<i>Cucurbita pepo</i> (Pumpkin peel extract)	SC-CO₂: 12g pumpkin peel, 15ml/min flow rate of CO ₂ , 0.25 ml/min of ethanol and water (%80 ethanol), 3h, 25MPa, 60°C SWE: R:1/15 g/ml, 3h, 5MPa,120°C	Total phenolic compounds (TPC) Total carotene SC-CO₂: 353.5±8.84 mgGA/100gE, 11.48±0.90 mg caretone/100gE SWE: 213.6±5.87 mgGA/100gE, 15.22±2.35 mg caretone/100gE	TPC of the extract was higher with SC-CO ₂ compared to SWE, while carotenoids amount was higher by SWE.	[116]

MAC: Maceration, SOX: Soxhlet, HWE: Hot water extraction, MAE: Microwave assisted extraction, UAE: Ultrasound assisted extraction, SC-CO₂: Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction, EAE: Enzyme assisted extraction, SWE: Subcritical water extraction, R: ratio of solid to solvent, g/ml

5 CONCLUSIONS

Efficiency, ease of processing, cost, time and product quality, physical-chemical properties of target compounds and raw material should be considered to decide on an appropriate extraction technique for target compounds from specific plant material. Generally, new extraction methods which include SC-CO₂, MAE, UAE, EAE, and PFE are promising methods to overcome the limitations of conventional methods. However, further research is required to accomplish these methods on an industrial scale by reducing the high cost of equipment and optimizing the process for each individual desired target compound from specific biomasses. Hence, more experimental analysis and modeling of these novel technologies are great of importance to making scale-up applications possible.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] M. Kehili *et al.*, "Biorefinery cascade processing for creating added value on tomato industrial by-products from Tunisia," *Biotechnology for biofuels*, vol. 9, p. 261, 2016, doi: 10.1186/s13068-016-0676-x.
- [2] V. G. Zuin and L. Z. Ramin, "Green and Sustainable Separation of Natural Products from Agro-Industrial Waste: Challenges, Potentialities, and Perspectives on Emerging Approaches," *Topics in current chemistry (Cham)*, vol. 376, no. 1, p. 3, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s41061-017-0182-z.
- [3] S. Ramaswamy, H.-J. Huang, and B. V. Ramarao, *Separation and Purification Technologies in Biorefineries*. Chichester, UK: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2013.
- [4] M. Aresta, A. Dibenedetto, and F. Dumeignil, *Biorefinery: From biomass to chemicals and fuels*. Berlin, Boston: Walter de Gruyter, 2012.
- [5] K. C. Badgujar, R. Dange, and B. M. Bhanage, "Recent advances of use of the supercritical carbon dioxide for the biomass pre-treatment and extraction: A mini-review," *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*, vol. 98, no. 1, p. 100018, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jics.2021.100018.
- [6] A.-E. Segneau, F. Szpile, P. Vlazan, P. Sfarloaga, I. Grozesku, and V. Daniel, "Biomass Extraction Methods," in *Biomass Now - Sustainable Growth and Use*, M. D. Matovic, Ed.: InTech, 2013.
- [7] G. Barjoveanu, O.-A. Pătrăuțanu, C. Teodosiu, and I. Volf, "Life cycle assessment of polyphenols extraction processes from waste biomass," *Scientific reports*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 13632, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-70587-w.
- [8] G. Moiceanu *et al.*, "Energy Consumption at Size Reduction of Lignocellulose Biomass for Bioenergy," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 9, p. 2477, 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11092477.
- [9] F. Chemat, N. Rombaut, A.-G. Sicaire, A. Meullemestre, A.-S. Fabiano-Tixier, and M. Abert-Vian, "Ultrasound assisted extraction of food and natural products. Mechanisms, techniques, combinations, protocols and applications. A review," *Ultrasonics sonochemistry*, vol. 34, pp. 540–560, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.ultsonch.2016.06.035.
- [10] D. Naviglio, P. Scarano, M. Ciaravolo, and M. Gallo, "Rapid Solid-Liquid Dynamic Extraction (RSLDE): A Powerful and Greener Alternative to the Latest Solid-Liquid Extraction Techniques," *Foods (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 8, no. 7, 2019, doi: 10.3390/foods8070245.
- [11] I. Cybulska, G. Brudecki, A. Allassali, M. Thomsen, and J. Brown, "Phytochemical composition of some common coastal halophytes of the United Arab Emirates," *Emir. J. Food Agric*, vol. 26, no. 12, p. 1046, 2014, doi: 10.9755/ejfa.v26i12.19104.
- [12] L. S. S. Hulkko, T. Chaturvedi, and M. H. Thomsen, "Extraction and Quantification of Chlorophylls, Carotenoids, Phenolic Compounds, and Vitamins from Halophyte Biomasses," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 2, p. 840, 2022, doi: 10.3390/app12020840.
- [13] Y. Wang, V. Herdegen, and J.-U. Repke, "Identification and analysis of mass transfer coefficients and effective diffusion coefficients for models of solvent extraction of Montan wax," *Separation Science and Technology*, vol. 51, no. 13, pp. 2183–2197, 2016, doi: 10.1080/01496395.2016.1202978.
- [14] Q.-W. Zhang, L.-G. Lin, and W.-C. Ye, "Techniques for extraction and isolation of natural products: a comprehensive review," *Chinese medicine*, vol. 13, p. 20, 2018, doi: 10.1186/s13020-018-0177-x.
- [15] *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*. Weinheim, Germany: Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, 2000.
- [16] Sofia Chanioti, George Liadakis, and Constatntina Tzia, "Solid-liquid Extraction," in *Contemporary Food Engineering series, Food engineering handbook: Food process engineering*, T. Varzakas, Ed., Boca Raton, Fla.: CRC Press, 2015, pp. 254–283.
- [17] Zurina Zainal Abidin, Dayang Radiah Awang Biak, "Separation and purification technologies in biorefineries: Solid-liquid extraction in biorefinery," in pp. 351–374.
- [18] B. Rodríguez-Martínez, B. Gullón, and R. Yáñez, "Identification and Recovery of Valuable Bioactive Compounds from Potato Peels: A Comprehensive Review," *Antioxidants (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 10, no. 10, 2021, doi: 10.3390/antiox10101630.
- [19] J. E. Sosa-Hernández, Z. Escobedo-Avellaneda, H. M. N. Iqbal, and J. Welti-Chanes, "State-of-the-Art Extraction Methodologies for Bioactive Compounds from Algal Biome to Meet Bio-Economy Challenges and Opportunities," *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 23, no. 11, 2018, doi: 10.3390/molecules23112953.
- [20] O. R. Alara, N. H. Abdurahman, and C. I. Ukaegbu, Eds., *Extraction of phenolic compounds: A review*, 2021.
- [21] Y. H. Chai *et al.*, "Valorization of Tropical Biomass Waste by Supercritical Fluid Extraction Technology," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 233, 2021, doi: 10.3390/su13010233.
- [22] J. Azmir *et al.*, "Techniques for extraction of bioactive compounds from plant materials: A review," *Journal of Food Engineering*, vol. 117, no. 4, pp. 426–436, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2013.01.014.
- [23] L. Wang and C. L. Weller, "Recent advances in extraction of nutraceuticals from plants," *Trends in*

- Food Science & Technology*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 300–312, 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.tifs.2005.12.004.
- [24] H. Passos, M. G. Freire, and J. A. P. Coutinho, “Ionic liquid solutions as extractive solvents for value-added compounds from biomass,” *Green chemistry : an international journal and green chemistry resource : GC*, vol. 16, no. 12, pp. 4786–4815, 2014, doi: 10.1039/c4gc00236a.
- [25] H. Ullah, C. D. Wilfred, and M. S. Shaharun, “Ionic liquid-based extraction and separation trends of bioactive compounds from plant biomass,” *Separation Science and Technology*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 559–579, 2019, doi: 10.1080/01496395.2018.1505913.
- [26] P. Xiao, C.-Y. Sun, W.-Q. Wang, and G.-J. Chen, “Modeling of the Solubility of Solids in Supercritical Fluids/Supercritical Fluids-Cosolvent Systems using Peng-Robinson Equation of State,” *Journal of Natural Gas Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 64–84, 2016, doi: 10.7569/JNGE.2015.692504.
- [27] M. HERRERO, A. CIFUENTES, and E. IBANEZ, “Sub- and supercritical fluid extraction of functional ingredients from different natural sources: Plants, food-by-products, algae and microalgae: A review,” *Food Chemistry*, vol. 98, no. 1, pp. 136–148, 2006, doi: 10.1016/J.FOODCHEM.2005.05.058.
- [28] K.-Y. Khaw, M.-O. Parat, P. N. Shaw, and J. R. Falconer, “Solvent Supercritical Fluid Technologies to Extract Bioactive Compounds from Natural Sources: A Review,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 22, no. 7, 2017, doi: 10.3390/molecules22071186.
- [29] K. Ghafoor, J. Park, and Y.-H. Choi, “Optimization of supercritical fluid extraction of bioactive compounds from grape (*Vitis labrusca* B.) peel by using response surface methodology,” *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 485–490, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2010.01.013.
- [30] R. K. Kankala, B.-Q. Chen, C.-G. Liu, H.-X. Tang, S.-B. Wang, and A.-Z. Chen, “Solution-enhanced dispersion by supercritical fluids: an ecofriendly nanonization approach for processing biomaterials and pharmaceutical compounds,” *International journal of nanomedicine*, vol. 13, pp. 4227–4245, 2018, doi: 10.2147/IJN.S166124.
- [31] K. Khosravi-Darani and E. Vashghani-Farahani, “Application of supercritical fluid extraction in biotechnology,” *Critical reviews in biotechnology*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 231–242, 2005, doi: 10.1080/07388550500354841.
- [32] F. Bezerra *et al.*, “Extraction of bioactive compounds,” in *Green Sustainable Process for Chemical and Environmental Engineering and Science*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 149–167.
- [33] M. Sauceau, J.-J. Letourneau, B. Freiss, D. Richon, and J. Fages, “Solubility of eflocimibe in supercritical carbon dioxide with or without a co-solvent,” *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 133–140, 2004, doi: 10.1016/j.supflu.2003.11.004.
- [34] H. İçen and M. Gürü, “Determination of Mass Transfer Coefficients on the Obtaining of Caffeine from Tea Stalk by Supercritical Carbon Dioxide With and Without Ethanol,” *Arab J Sci Eng*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 2257–2262, 2018, doi: 10.1007/s13369-017-2684-y.
- [35] J. Wang *et al.*, “Separation of Biomass Pyrolysis Oil by Supercritical CO₂ Extraction,” *SGRE*, vol. 01, no. 02, pp. 98–107, 2010, doi: 10.4236/sgre.2010.12015.
- [36] K. Ameer, H. M. Shahbaz, and J.-H. Kwon, “Green Extraction Methods for Polyphenols from Plant Matrices and Their Byproducts: A Review,” *Comprehensive reviews in food science and food safety*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 295–315, 2017, doi: 10.1111/1541-4337.12253.
- [37] B. A. S. Machado, C. G. Pereira, S. B. Nunes, F. F. Padilha, and M. A. Umsza-Guez, “Supercritical Fluid Extraction Using CO₂: Main Applications and Future Perspectives,” *Separation Science and Technology*, vol. 48, no. 18, pp. 2741–2760, 2013, doi: 10.1080/01496395.2013.811422.
- [38] M. Raventós, S. Duarte, and R. Alarcón, “Application and Possibilities of Supercritical CO₂ Extraction in Food Processing Industry: An Overview,” *Food sci. technol. int.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 269–284, 2002, doi: 10.1106/108201302029451.
- [39] P. A. Uwineza and A. Waśkiewicz, “Recent Advances in Supercritical Fluid Extraction of Natural Bioactive Compounds from Natural Plant Materials,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 25, no. 17, 2020, doi: 10.3390/molecules25173847.
- [40] S. H. Soh, S. Agarwal, A. Jain, L. Y. Lee, S. K. Chin, and S. Jayaraman, “Mathematical modeling of mass transfer in supercritical fluid extraction of patchouli oil,” *Engineering Reports*, vol. 1, no. 4, 2019, doi: 10.1002/eng2.12051.
- [41] M. Pilavtepe, M. Yucel, S. S. Helvacı, M. Demircioglu, and O. Yesil-Celiktas, “Optimization and mathematical modeling of mass transfer between *Zostera marina* residues and supercritical CO₂ modified with ethanol,” *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, vol. 68, pp. 87–93, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.supflu.2012.04.013.
- [42] O. Döker, U. Salgın, İ. Şanal, Ü. Mehmetoğlu, and A. Çalımlı, “Modeling of extraction of β -carotene from apricot bagasse using supercritical CO₂ in packed bed extractor,” *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 11–19, 2004, doi: 10.1016/S0896-8446(03)00006-8.
- [43] K. Aladić *et al.*, “Supercritical CO₂ extraction of hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) seed oil,” *Industrial Crops and Products*, vol. 76, pp. 472–478, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2015.07.016.
- [44] M. Kehili *et al.*, “Supercritical CO₂ extraction and antioxidant activity of lycopene and β -carotene-enriched oleoresin from tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* L.) peels by-product of a Tunisian industry,” *Food and Bioproducts Processing*, vol. 102, pp. 340–349, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.fbp.2017.02.002.
- [45] S. A. Radzali, M. Markom, and N. M. Saleh, “Co-Solvent Selection for Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SFE) of Phenolic Compounds from *Labisia pumila*,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 25, no. 24, 2020, doi: 10.3390/molecules25245859.
- [46] E. Destandau, T. Michel, and C. Elfakir, “CHAPTER 4. Microwave-assisted Extraction,” in *Green Chemistry Series, Natural Product Extraction*, M. A. Rostagno and J. M. Prado, Eds., Cambridge: Royal Society of Chemistry, 2013, pp. 113–156.

- [47] S. B. Bagade and M. Patil, "Recent Advances in Microwave Assisted Extraction of Bioactive Compounds from Complex Herbal Samples: A Review," *Critical reviews in analytical chemistry*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 138–149, 2021, doi: 10.1080/10408347.2019.1686966.
- [48] V. Lopez-Avila and M. D. Luque de Castro, "Microwave-Assisted Extraction," in *Reference Module in Chemistry, Molecular Sciences and Chemical Engineering*: Elsevier, 2014.
- [49] L. López-Hortas, M. D. Torres, and H. Domínguez, "Equipment and recent advances in microwave processing," in *Innovative and Emerging Technologies in the Bio-marine Food Sector*: Elsevier, 2022, pp. 333–360.
- [50] J. M. Danlami, A. Arsad, M. A. Ahmad Zaini, and H. Sulaiman, "A comparative study of various oil extraction techniques from plants," *Reviews in Chemical Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 6, 2014, doi: 10.1515/revce-2013-0038.
- [51] T. Belwal *et al.*, "Recent advances in scaling-up of non-conventional extraction techniques: Learning from successes and failures," *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 127, p. 115895, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.trac.2020.115895.
- [52] W. Routray and V. Orsat, "Microwave-Assisted Extraction of Flavonoids: A Review," *Food Bioprocess Technol*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 409–424, 2012, doi: 10.1007/s11947-011-0573-z.
- [53] A. Hamid Nour, A. Ruth Oluwaseun, A. Hamid Nour, M. Suliman Omer, and N. Ahmed, "Microwave-Assisted Extraction of Bioactive Compounds (Review)," in *Microwave Heating - Electromagnetic Fields Causing Thermal and Non-Thermal Effects*, G. I. Churyumov, Ed.: IntechOpen, 2021.
- [54] S. Deo *et al.*, "Emerging Microwave Assisted Extraction (MAE) techniques as an innovative green technologies for the effective extraction of the active phytopharmaceuticals," *Rese. Jour. of Pharm. and Technol.*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 655, 2015, doi: 10.5958/0974-360X.2015.00104.3.
- [55] L. Sanchez-Prado, C. Garcia-Jares, and M. Llompert, "Microwave-assisted extraction: Application to the determination of emerging pollutants in solid samples," *Journal of chromatography. A*, vol. 1217, no. 16, pp. 2390–2414, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.chroma.2009.11.080.
- [56] J. L. Luque-García, "EXTRACTION | Microwave-Assisted Solvent Extraction," in *Encyclopedia of Analytical Science*: Elsevier, 2005, pp. 584–591.
- [57] C.-H. Chan, R. Yusoff, G.-C. Ngoh, and F. W.-L. Kung, "Microwave-assisted extractions of active ingredients from plants," *Journal of chromatography. A*, vol. 1218, no. 37, pp. 6213–6225, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.chroma.2011.07.040.
- [58] F.-G. C. Ekezie, D.-W. Sun, and J.-H. Cheng, "Acceleration of microwave-assisted extraction processes of food components by integrating technologies and applying emerging solvents: A review of latest developments," *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, vol. 67, pp. 160–172, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.tifs.2017.06.006.
- [59] L. Gomez, B. Tiwari, and M. Garcia-Vaquero, "Emerging extraction techniques: Microwave-assisted extraction," in *Sustainable Seaweed Technologies*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 207–224.
- [60] T. Tsiaka, V. J. Sinanoglou, and P. Zoumpoulakis, "Extracting Bioactive Compounds From Natural Sources Using Green High-Energy Approaches: Trends and Opportunities in Lab- and Large-Scale Applications," in *Ingredients Extraction by Physicochemical Methods in Food*: Elsevier, 2017, pp. 307–365.
- [61] I. Michalak and K. Chojnacka, "Algal extracts: Technology and advances," *Eng. Life Sci.*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 581–591, 2014, doi: 10.1002/elsc.201400139.
- [62] Y. Li, M. Radoiu, A.-S. Fabiano-Tixier, and F. Chemat, "From Laboratory to Industry: Scale-Up, Quality, and Safety Consideration for Microwave-Assisted Extraction," in *Food Engineering Series, Microwave-assisted Extraction for Bioactive Compounds*, F. Chemat and G. Cravotto, Eds., Boston, MA: Springer US, 2013, pp. 207–229.
- [63] C.-H. Chan, R. Yusoff, and G. C. Ngoh, "An Energy-Based Approach to Scale Up Microwave-Assisted Extraction of Plant Bioactives," in *Ingredients Extraction by Physicochemical Methods in Food*: Elsevier, 2017, pp. 561–597.
- [64] Y. Li, S. Li, S.-J. Lin, J.-J. Zhang, C.-N. Zhao, and H.-B. Li, "Microwave-Assisted Extraction of Natural Antioxidants from the Exotic *Gordonia axillaris* Fruit: Optimization and Identification of Phenolic Compounds," *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 22, no. 9, 2017, doi: 10.3390/molecules22091481.
- [65] E.-Q. Xia, B. Cui, X.-R. Xu, Y. Song, X.-X. Ai, and H.-B. Li, "Microwave-assisted extraction of oxymatrine from *Sophora flavescens*," *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 9, pp. 7391–7400, 2011, doi: 10.3390/molecules16097391.
- [66] N. A. Zamanhuri, N. A. Rahman, and N. F. A. Bakar, "Effect of Microwave Power and Extraction Time on Crude Palm Oil Quality Using Microwave-Assisted Extraction Process," *IJRED*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 495–505, 2021, doi: 10.14710/ijred.2021.35402.
- [67] A. Liazid, M. Palma, J. Brigui, and C. G. Barroso, "Investigation on phenolic compounds stability during microwave-assisted extraction," *Journal of chromatography. A*, vol. 1140, 1-2, pp. 29–34, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.chroma.2006.11.040.
- [68] A. V. B. Reddy, M. Moniruzzaman, V. Madhavi, and J. Jaafar, "Recent improvements in the extraction, cleanup and quantification of bioactive flavonoids," in *Studies in Natural Products Chemistry, Bioactive Natural Products*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 197–223.
- [69] K. Vilku, R. Mawson, L. Simons, and D. Bates, "Applications and opportunities for ultrasound assisted extraction in the food industry — A review," *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 161–169, 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2007.04.014.
- [70] A. Carreira-Casais *et al.*, "Benefits and Drawbacks of Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction for the Recovery of Bioactive Compounds from Marine Algae," *International journal of environmental research and public health*, vol. 18, no. 17, 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph18179153.
- [71] S. Roohinejad, N. Nikmaram, M. Brahim, M. Koubaa, A. Khelfa, and R. Greiner, "Potential of Novel Technologies for Aqueous Extraction of

- Plant Bioactives,” in *Water Extraction of Bioactive Compounds*: Elsevier, 2017, pp. 399–419.
- [72] A. Syahir, S. Sulaiman, M. Mel, M. Othman, and S. Zubaidah Sulaiman, “An Overview: Analysis of ultrasonic-assisted extraction’s parameters and its process,” *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 778, no. 1, p. 12165, 2020, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/778/1/012165.
- [73] J. F. Osorio-Tobón, “Recent advances and comparisons of conventional and alternative extraction techniques of phenolic compounds,” *Journal of food science and technology*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 4299–4315, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s13197-020-04433-2.
- [74] J. Pains, V. Benedetti, S. S. Ail, M. J. Castaldi, M. Baratieri, and F. Patuzzi, “Valorization of Wastes from the Food Production Industry: A Review Towards an Integrated Agri-Food Processing Biorefinery,” *Waste Biomass Valor*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 31–50, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12649-021-01467-1.
- [75] A. Chahardoli, F. Jalilian, Z. Memariani, M. H. Farzaei, and Y. Shokohinia, “Analysis of organic acids,” in *Recent Advances in Natural Products Analysis*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 767–823.
- [76] Z. Yi, Y. Su, S. Brynjolfsson, K. Olafsdóttir, and W. Fu, “Bioactive polysaccharides and their derivatives from microalgae: biosynthesis, applications, and challenges,” in *Studies in Natural Products Chemistry*: Elsevier, 2021, pp. 67–85.
- [77] Daniella Pingret, Anne-Sylvie Fabiano-Tixier, and Farid Chemat, “CHAPTER 3:Ultrasound-assisted Extraction,” in *Natural Product Extraction*, 2013, pp. 89–112. [Online]. Available: <https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/chapter/9781849737579-00089/978-1-84973-757-9>
- [78] D. Panda and S. Manickam, “Cavitation Technology—The Future of Greener Extraction Method: A Review on the Extraction of Natural Products and Process Intensification Mechanism and Perspectives,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 4, p. 766, 2019, doi: 10.3390/app9040766.
- [79] I. Lavilla and C. Bendicho, “Fundamentals of Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction,” in *Water Extraction of Bioactive Compounds*: Elsevier, 2017, pp. 291–316.
- [80] F.-J. Cui *et al.*, “Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction of Polysaccharides from *Volvariella volvacea*: Process Optimization and Structural Characterization,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 23, no. 7, 2018, doi: 10.3390/molecules23071706.
- [81] N. Moradi, M. Rahimi, A. Moeni, and M. A. Parsamoghadam, “Impact of ultrasound on oil yield and content of functional food ingredients at the oil extraction from sunflower,” *Separation Science and Technology*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 261–276, 2018, doi: 10.1080/01496395.2017.1384016.
- [82] A. Altemimi, R. Choudhary, D. G. Watson, and D. A. Lightfoot, “Effects of ultrasonic treatments on the polyphenol and antioxidant content of spinach extracts,” *Ultrasonics sonochemistry*, vol. 24, pp. 247–255, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ultsonch.2014.10.023.
- [83] M. Puri, D. Sharma, and C. J. Barrow, “Enzyme-assisted extraction of bioactives from plants,” *Trends in biotechnology*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 37–44, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.tibtech.2011.06.014.
- [84] Baby K C, Ranganathan thottiam Vasudevan, “Enzyme -Assisted extraction of Bioingredients,” 2013.
- [85] P. Streimikyte, P. Viskelis, and J. Viskelis, “Enzymes-Assisted Extraction of Plants for Sustainable and Functional Applications,” *International journal of molecular sciences*, vol. 23, no. 4, 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijms23042359.
- [86] Giselle Franca-Oliveira and Tiziana Fornari and Blanca Hernández-Ledesma, “A Review on the Extraction and Processing of Natural Source-Derived Proteins through Eco-Innovative Approaches,”
- [87] C. M. Ajila, S. K. Brar, M. Verma, R. D. Tyagi, S. Godbout, and J. R. Valéro, “Extraction and analysis of polyphenols: recent trends,” *Critical reviews in biotechnology*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 227–249, 2011, doi: 10.3109/07388551.2010.513677.
- [88] M. Calderón-Oliver and E. Ponce-Alquicira, “Environmentally Friendly Techniques and Their Comparison in the Extraction of Natural Antioxidants from Green Tea, Rosemary, Clove, and Oregano,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 26, no. 7, 2021, doi: 10.3390/molecules26071869.
- [89] S. C. Mandal, *Herbal Biomolecules in Healthcare Applications*. San Diego: Elsevier Science & Technology, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/kxp/detail.action?docID=6745780>
- [90] J. Liu, M. A. A. Gasmalla, P. Li, and R. Yang, “Enzyme-assisted extraction processing from oilseeds: Principle, processing and application,” *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 35, pp. 184–193, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2016.05.002.
- [91] E. M. C. Alexandre, S. A. Moreira, L. M. G. Castro, M. Pintado, and J. A. Saraiva, “Emerging technologies to extract high value compounds from fruit residues: Sub/supercritical, ultrasound-, and enzyme-assisted extractions,” *Food Reviews International*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 581–612, 2018, doi: 10.1080/87559129.2017.1359842.
- [92] Y.-M. Zhao, J. Wang, Z.-G. Wu, J.-M. Yang, W. Li, and L.-X. Shen, “Extraction, purification and anti-proliferative activities of polysaccharides from *Lentinus edodes*,” *International journal of biological macromolecules*, vol. 93, Pt A, pp. 136–144, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.05.100.
- [93] T. B. Huy, N. T. Lien Phuong, B. K. Nga, H. N. Oanh, and N. H. Hieu, “Enzyme-Assisted Extraction of Triterpenoid Saponins from *Pseuderanthemum palatiferum* (Nees) Radlk. Dry Leaf Powder and Bioactivities Examination of Extracts,” *ChemistrySelect*, vol. 4, no. 27, pp. 8129–8134, 2019, doi: 10.1002/slct.201900778.
- [94] G. Alvarez-Rivera, M. Bueno, D. Ballesteros-Vivas, J. A. Mendiola, and E. Ibañez, “Pressurized Liquid Extraction,” in *Liquid-Phase Extraction*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 375–398.
- [95] A. Nieto, F. Borrull, E. Pocurull, and R. M. Marcé, “Pressurized liquid extraction: A useful technique to extract pharmaceuticals and personal-care products from sewage sludge,” *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 29, no. 7, pp. 752–764, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.trac.2010.03.014.
- [96] M. U. Rehman, Abdullah, F. Khan, and K. Niaz, “Introduction to natural products analysis,” in

- Recent Advances in Natural Products Analysis*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 3–15.
- [97] A. Mustafa and C. Turner, “Pressurized liquid extraction as a green approach in food and herbal plants extraction: A review,” *Analytica chimica acta*, vol. 703, no. 1, pp. 8–18, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.aca.2011.07.018.
- [98] M. Hironart, N. Rombaut, A. S. Fabiano-Tixier, A. Bily, and F. Chemat, “Comparison between Pressurized Liquid Extraction and Conventional Soxhlet Extraction for Rosemary Antioxidants, Yield, Composition, and Environmental Footprint,” *Foods (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 9, no. 5, 2020, doi: 10.3390/foods9050584.
- [99] N. Nastić *et al.*, “Subcritical water extraction as an environmentally-friendly technique to recover bioactive compounds from traditional Serbian medicinal plants,” *Industrial Crops and Products*, vol. 111, pp. 579–589, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2017.11.015.
- [100] A. Haghghi and M. Khajenoori, “Subcritical Water Extraction,” in *Mass Transfer - Advances in Sustainable Energy and Environment Oriented Numerical Modeling*, H. Nakajima, Ed.: InTech, 2013.
- [101] M. Castro-Puyana, M. HERRERO, J. A. Mendiola, and E. Ibáñez, “Subcritical water extraction of bioactive components from algae,” in *Functional Ingredients from Algae for Foods and Nutraceuticals*: Elsevier, 2013, pp. 534–560.
- [102] Z. Lorigooini, F. Jamshidi-kia, and S. Dodman, “Analysis of sesquiterpenes and sesquiterpenoids,” in *Recent Advances in Natural Products Analysis*: Elsevier, 2020, pp. 289–312.
- [103] Y. Cheng, F. Xue, S. Yu, S. Du, and Y. Yang, “Subcritical Water Extraction of Natural Products,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 26, no. 13, 2021, doi: 10.3390/molecules26134004.
- [104] R. Carabias-Martínez, E. Rodríguez-Gonzalo, P. Revilla-Ruiz, and J. Hernández-Méndez, “Pressurized liquid extraction in the analysis of food and biological samples,” *Journal of chromatography. A*, vol. 1089, 1-2, pp. 1–17, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.chroma.2005.06.072.
- [105] J. Zhang, C. Wen, H. Zhang, Y. Duan, and H. Ma, “Recent advances in the extraction of bioactive compounds with subcritical water: A review,” *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, vol. 95, pp. 183–195, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.tifs.2019.11.018.
- [106] H. Di Domenico Ziero, L. S. Buller, A. Mudhoo, L. C. Ampese, S. I. Mussatto, and T. F. Carneiro, “An overview of subcritical and supercritical water treatment of different biomasses for protein and amino acids production and recovery,” *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 104406, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jece.2020.104406.
- [107] M.-J. Ko, H.-L. Kwon, and M.-S. Chung, “Pilot-scale subcritical water extraction of flavonoids from satsuma mandarin (Citrus unshiu Markovich) peel,” *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, vol. 38, pp. 175–181, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ifset.2016.10.008.
- [108] C. I. Rivas-Vela, S. L. Amaya-Llano, E. Castaño-Tostado, and G. A. Castillo-Herrera, “Protein Hydrolysis by Subcritical Water: A New Perspective on Obtaining Bioactive Peptides,” *Molecules (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 26, no. 21, 2021, doi: 10.3390/molecules26216655.
- [109] D. Lachos-Perez, F. Martínez-Jimenez, C. A. Rezende, G. Tompsett, M. Timko, and T. Forster-Carneiro, “Subcritical water hydrolysis of sugarcane bagasse: An approach on solid residues characterization,” *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, vol. 108, pp. 69–78, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.supflu.2015.10.019.
- [110] G. L. Zabot, E. R. Abaide, M. V. Tres, and M. A. Mazutti, “Subcritical Hydrolysis Contribution in the Holistic Biorefinery Concept: Obtaining Bioproducts and Biofuels From Renewable Natural Resources for a Novel Bioeconomy,” in *Advanced Bioprocessing for Alternative Fuels, Biobased Chemicals, and Bioproducts*: Elsevier, 2019, pp. 35–57.
- [111] X. Liang and Q. Fan, “Application of Sub-Critical Water Extraction in Pharmaceutical Industry,” *MSCE*, vol. 01, no. 05, pp. 1–6, 2013, doi: 10.4236/msce.2013.15001.
- [112] C. M. Galanakis, Ed., *Emerging technologies for the recovery of bioactive compounds from saffron species*, 1st ed. Waltham: Elsevier, 2020.
- [113] J. Zhang, L. Yang, and H. Liu, “Green and Efficient Processing of Wood with Supercritical CO₂: A Review,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 9, p. 3929, 2021, doi: 10.3390/app11093929.
- [114] T. C. Ho and B.-S. Chun, “Extraction of Bioactive Compounds from *Pseuderanthemum palatiferum* (Nees) Radlk. Using Subcritical Water and Conventional Solvents: A Comparison Study,” *Journal of food science*, vol. 84, no. 5, pp. 1201–1207, 2019, doi: 10.1111/1750-3841.14501.
- [115] P. Mašković *et al.*, “Summer savory extracts prepared by novel extraction methods resulted in enhanced biological activity,” *Industrial Crops and Products*, vol. 109, pp. 875–881, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.indcrop.2017.09.063.
- [116] A. Salami, N. Asefi, R. E. Kenari, and M. Gharekhani, “Extraction of pumpkin peel extract using supercritical CO₂ and subcritical water technology: Enhancing oxidative stability of canola oil,” *Journal of food science and technology*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 1101–1109, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s13197-020-04624-x.
- [117] R. Bruni, A. Guerrini, S. Scalia, C. Romagnoli, and G. Sacchetti, “Rapid techniques for the extraction of vitamin E isomers from *Amaranthus caudatus* seeds: ultrasonic and supercritical fluid extraction,” *Phytochemical analysis : PCA*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 257–261, 2002, doi: 10.1002/pca.651.
- [118] M. Molnar, N. Mendešević, D. Šubarić, I. Banjari, and S. Jokić, “Comparison of various techniques for the extraction of umbelliferone and herniarin in *Matricaria chamomilla* processing fractions,” *Chemistry Central journal*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 78, 2017, doi: 10.1186/s13065-017-0308-y.
- [119] H. van Le and V. M. van Le, “Comparison of enzyme-assisted and ultrasound-assisted extraction of vitamin C and phenolic compounds from acerola (*Malpighia emarginata* DC.) fruit,” *International Journal of Food Science & Technology*, vol. 47, no. 6, pp. 1206–1214, 2012, doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2621.2012.02960.x.

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 862834. Any results of this project reflect only this consortium's view and the European Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

8 LOGO SPACE

